

INNOVATIVE DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract. *The main aspects of the concept "digital economy", its characteristic features are considered in this article. Besides, the concept "digital economy" from the standard point of view and scientific treatment is defined, its basic components are specified. Standard and legal regulation of digital economy in our republic, tasks and the objects set for its development in our state is defined.*

Keywords: *digital economy, development, state, components.*

The large-scale involvement of the latest software and technical tools of modern technological development in the educational system allows training personnel who can meet all the most serious requirements of the current era. One such tool is the open distance education system on digital platforms, which allows people to get a full-fledged education without being separated from production and other daily tasks. It has become a daily necessity in today's quarantine period. The task now is how this need can be organized qualitatively. It is known that an open distance education system on digital platforms should include lectures, and lectures should include all necessary materials, tests and final controls. Classes should be organized only online. The problem is, is each student logging into the platform and getting the relevant information, or is another student logging in instead? There is no way to determine this.

At present, the digital economy and a number of effective technologies related to it are rapidly entering our lives. For the same reason, in order to further accelerate the development of the state and society, the leadership of our Republic made several important decisions. For example, in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoev to the Oliy Majlis on December 28, 2018, about the most important priority tasks for 2019, he mentioned the following about the development of the digital economy in our country: "All sectors of the economy will be developed on the basis of digital technologies. We need to develop a "National Concept of Digital Economy" that envisages its renewal. On this basis, we need to implement the "Digital Uzbekistan-2030" program. The digital economy allows to increase the gross domestic product by at least 30% and reduce corruption sharply. Analyzes conducted by reputable international organizations confirm this. Therefore, the Government is tasked with developing a "roadmap" for the transition to the digital economy within two months. In this regard, it is necessary to pay special attention to information security." That is why the issues of how to develop it are facing society and the people. In this article, we discuss the role of the digital economy in the educational system and some directions of the development strategy in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The modern educational process strives for universalization using digital technologies and models people as maximally similar to each other in education (that is, requires compatibility). Modern schools and universities imagine their students in the form of classic "black boxes", give them all the same information and expect a response from them without taking into account the individual characteristics of the learners. Such an approach is understood by many as an

anachronism of the industrial age, which should be abandoned already. Some propose to solve this problem by involving more teachers in the educational process.

Because in this, special attention is paid to each student, and the educational process can be organized optimally, taking into account their needs and abilities. But since this is a very expensive activity, many experts in pedagogy emphasize that the use of software and technical tools and capabilities of modern computers in the educational process can lead to good results. If this path is followed, in the future computers would be able to create individual educational programs for each pupil or student in accordance with his intellectual, emotional and knowledge level with the help of appropriate software and technical support.

Currently, a number of developed countries in the world (USA, China, Japan, EU countries, Russia, etc.), taking into account the changes that have begun to take place in the world economy, are starting an intensive effort to digitize most sectors of the economy. However, considering these data, we must note that none, including the leading countries, have a complete philosophical understanding of what the digital economy is and what consequences it may have in the future. It seems that many countries do not understand the digital economy as new forms of economic relations and management, but rather new digital forms of communication and payments with consumers. Most countries do not consciously organize a digital economy, but are engaged in the process of digitizing existing economic relations.

The process of organizing the digital economy in Uzbekistan can be divided into the following four main blocks:

- Creating the necessary conditions for the development of the digital economy (that is, creating the appropriate legal framework).
- Emergence of digital economy platforms in economic entities that are most ready for digital transformation and launch on a global scale.
- Digital economy platform competition and their gradual integration.
- Introducing the most convenient solutions in the field of digital economy to the entire economy.

In our country, we have chosen such a strategy for the development of the digital economy, which has been tested in the USA and China.

There are still a number of problems that need to be solved in the field of education, but these problems will be solved by passionate professors and teachers in the near future. In this context, we would like to mention our suggestions and conclusions: the development of the digital economy is one of the issues of strategic importance for the Republic of Uzbekistan, which determines its global competitiveness. This means that it is necessary to create conditions for the development of the digital economy in our country, to direct it to the most necessary areas, and to stimulate this process at the level of possibility. In our opinion, when creating digital economy platforms, it is necessary to focus on the following areas: telecommunications, energy, transport, health care, taxation and taxation, medicine logistics, data processing, tourism, foreign economic activity, real estate sales and production. It is the development of these areas that allows creating the necessary infrastructure and a suitable technological base. Then, moving them to other areas of the economy, it will be possible to form the digital economy in Uzbekistan as quickly as possible. Such an approach seems appropriate for our republic today, but it is certainly not without its shortcomings.

Development trends in life clearly show that other services of the digital economy, including artificial intelligence, machine learning and various other technologies, will play a

decisive role in the future economy and corporate governance. In order to carry out these tasks, it is necessary to train specialists who can fully understand and apply the digital economy in higher education institutions. year is appropriate. Every subject teacher should understand the place of digital economy in his subject and convey it to his students. In any case, today the professors and teachers of the Navoi State Pedagogical Institute are making good use of the digital platform.

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